

Profitability of Low Energy District Heating for Areas with Low Energy Buildings

Inese Nagla

DTU BYG, Technical University of Denmark
S071217@student.dtu.dk

Vision

The main areas of improvements

Metering system

- High labor costs, increases with user complains
- Remote metering
- New ways of control
- New tariffs, fines, rewards

User behavior

- Huge influence on energy consumption
- More information, advice
- Motivating tariffs (max cooling of return water)
- Good system design

Energy demand in the buildings

- Should be reduced as much as possible
- Measurements of real consumption

Number of connected consumers to the DH network

- What is the limit when DH is still profitable?
- Users as suppliers
- Information about benefits of DH
- New laws

Optimization of the DH network

- New types of pipes
- Supply pipe with circulation
- Decentralized pumping

Energy regulations

- It is not mandatory to connect to DH – should it be changed?
- From 2015 “Renewable Energy” factor of 0.8 for DH
- Introduction of energy labeling for heat exchangers and pipes
- Incentive tariffs by laws
- Increased energy and CO₂ tax

Economical considerations

- Decreased construction costs (with flex-pipes)
- Available credits of more than 25 years
- Public institutions support individual users
- ESCO financing for changing individual units

Energy supply

- Based on renewable energy
- Best available local sources
- Several sources integrated in the common network

Energy storage

- Electricity storage and heat pumps
- Improvement of heat storage

Building energy simulations in IDA ICE

Human behavior influence on the heating demand in low energy buildings

Why low energy district heating is so promising?

...BUT

As heating requirement is predicted to be very low in low energy buildings, the cost-effectiveness of DH systems is affected by high investment and operational costs, in comparison to the income from the delivered heat

How to make DH systems competitive for areas with low energy buildings??

Workshop

District heating network simulations in TERMIS

Twin pipes with very small diameters for decreased heat loss

Case study – low energy district heating network in Lystrup

